

Edible Jumpers Powered by Shell Snapping

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Food animation is gaining increasing attention for the ability to reduce waste and increase attractiveness in animals and humans. Although several examples of food animation methods have been recently described, the speed and range of motion are still limited. Here a method is described to design and manufacture small edible jumpers powered by rapid release of elastic energy through shell snapping. The jumping actuators are made of gelatin crosslinked with genipin and polyvinyl alcohol, ensuring resilience to stress during shell eversion. The shape and size of the shells are modeled and optimized for maximum jumping height resulting in jumpers with a diameter of 47 mm that can reach a jumping height of 361 mm. The edible jumpers can be loaded with additional nutritional components encapsulated by humidity-sensitive latches for automatic release. To showcase potential uses of such edible jumpers, a jumping food pellet for pets and an animated dessert for humans are described.

Here we describe fully edible and untethered jumpers that can be loaded with customizable nutrition. These edible jumpers display fast and large displacement by rapidly releasing stored elastic energy when triggered by mechanical or chemical stimulation, akin to jumping mechanisms adopted by small animals, such as fleas and click beetles.^[28,29] Non-edible jumpers that leverage stored elastic energy are often made of metal or soft elastomers (Figure 1) and are triggered by external stimulation (marked with black circles in Figure 1)^[12–18] or by onboard actuators,^[19–26] which however come at the cost of added mass and size. Some non-edible jumpers are tethered to a pump or battery^[19–22,27] to store and release elastic

energy; others, instead, rely on heat,^[12] solvent,^[13,14] and light^[15–17] but require wireless power sources or toxic solvents. Manually-loaded elastic energy has been used for a micro-jumper made from MEMS (microelectromechanical systems) device, but it was inedible.^[18]

Here we leverage the principle of snap-buckling of soft shells^[30] to design, model, and prototype edible jumpers that display comparable or better jumping height than non-edible, soft, and untethered jumpers (Figure 1). The proposed edible jumper resembles a rubbery toy popper or a bimetallic jumping disk used for children and pet entertainment,^[31] suggesting that it could add a positive surprise element to animated food. We describe a method for synthesizing and characterizing edible jumping materials, a model for relating jumping properties to jumper dimensions, and the experimental validation of edible jumpers with and without an additional edible payload. Finally, as a proof of concept, we describe two use cases of edible jumpers: animated food for pets and animated dessert for humans.

1. Introduction

There is an increasing interest for food that can change color, smell, and shape prior to consumption.^[1,2] In particular, animated food can attract attention because it defies expectations and make it more palatable for both humans and animals.^[3–5] Examples of animated food include pasta that morphs into predefined shapes when tossed in boiling water,^[6] edible origami cubes that slowly unfold to reveal enclosed food items when drizzled with a low pH-liquid, such as lemon juice,^[7] and a partly edible cucumber that buries itself into a bed of rice bran to slowly ferment into pickle.^[8] However, current animated food moves slowly and displays small range of motion^[9] that requires persistent attention from the eater. Recent work on faster animated food, such as flyers with edible wings^[10] and rolling wheels with edible bodies, sensors and legs,^[11] still rely non-edible components for generating faster and larger range of motion.

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2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Material Selection

A snap buckling mechanism requires the identification of edible materials capable of storing elastic energy produced by shell inversion (Figure 1, inset image). This stored energy is released when the inverted shell snap-buckles into its initial shape, thus triggering the jumping motion. We compiled the Young's modulus (E) and tensile strength (σ_{TS}) of inedible materials^[12,16,20,23,24,27,32–36] that were used for jumping by snap buckling to quantitatively compare the maximum elastic energy stored per unit volume W (Figure 2a), where $W = 0.5\sigma_{TS}^2/E$.^[37]

Figure 1. Comparison of the maximum jumping heights (h) versus body length (BL) of inedible jumpers in^[12–27] and this work. Materials used to store the elastic energy were distinguished with different marker colors (blue: metal; orange: soft elastomers; green: edible materials proposed in this work). Jumpers indicated by black circles rely on external stimuli to trigger jumping.^[12–18] Tethered jumpers (hollow markers) are physically connected to an external power source (e.g., pump, battery) to store and release elastic energy.^[19–22,27]

In this work, we used gelatin as a base material because it is chewable, its E value is comparable to that of silicone elastomers (e.g., PDMS; polydimethylsiloxane, Elite Double 32), and its mechanical properties can be tuned by a diverse set of edible additives.^[38–40] The range of E and σ_{TS} of our gelatin mixture is depicted as a yellow region in Figure 2a. Although the highest σ_{TS}^2/E of our gelatin (2.8 MJ m^{-3}) is still lower than that of silicone elastomers, steel, and shape memory alloy, it is greater than that of heat-responsive jumping gel. To the best of our knowledge, this work is the only case of using an edible material (gelatin) to store and release elastic energy.

Our proposed material combines gelatin (Gel) with glycerol (Gly), water (Wat), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), and genipin (Gen) to increase W . Glycerol and water were used as plasticizers to maintain softness whereas PVA and genipin were used to increase mechanical strength. PVA, which is used in food and medical applications due to its very low toxicity,^[41] interacts with gelatin via hydrogen bonds to increase E and σ_{TS} .^[39,42] Genipin, which is used to enhance food texture and shelf life,^[43] is a protein crosslinker that forms a strong gelatinous network.^[40] Here, we set the mass ratios of gelatin, glycerol, water, and genipin to 1:2.5:2.5:0.01, building on a mixture ratio that we previously used for a gelatin-based gripper; namely Gel:Gly:Wat:Gen = 1:2:3:0.^[38] However, here the glycerol ratio was increased (from 2 to 2.5) to improve elasticity while the water ratio was decreased (from 3 to 2.5) to reduce volumetric shrinkage of gelatin over time.^[44] In addition, here we added genipin up to 1% of the gelatin mass, as over-crosslinking with genipin can decrease the toughness of gelatin.^[40] By fixing the 1:2.5:2.5:0.01 (Gel:Gly:Wat:Gen) ratio as a constant, five Gel:PVA mass ratios (1:0, 1:0.05, 1:0.10, 1:0.15, and 1:0.20) were mechanically tested to measure the change of

E , σ_{TS} , and elongation at break (EAB), and identify an optimal PVA ratio that yields the highest W . Please refer to the Materials and Method for more details on the fabrication process of the gelatin samples.

E values of samples with five different Gel:PVA ratios increased over time and stabilized after a week (Figure 2b). The change in E is caused by the rearrangement of the gelatin network, which can continue for weeks depending on material mixture ratios.^[45,46] While σ_{TS} fluctuated between 0.3 and 1.1 MPa for ten days, the largest σ_{TS} was achieved with a mixture that included PVA (Figure 2c), indicating that the addition of PVA is beneficial for withstanding higher stress. EAB decreased for ten days regardless of PVA contents and was caused by the formation of new crosslinks over time^[46] (Figure 2d). All the measured E and σ_{TS} are also depicted inside the yellow area (labelled with “This work”) in Figure 2a where the largest σ_{TS}^2/E measured from our gelatin mixtures was 2.8 MJ m^{-3} (Figure 2a).

These E , σ_{TS} , and EAB measurements were then repeated by replacing genipin with transglutaminase (TG), as it is edible and widely used to crosslink protein (including gelatin).^[48] By maintaining the 1:2.5:2.5:0.01 mass ratio for Gel:Gly:Wat:Gen, five mass ratios of Gel:PVA (1:0, 1:0.05, 1:0.10, 1:0.15, and 1:0.20) were considered analogously to the previous experiments. Overall, E and σ_{TS} values of samples crosslinked with TG were smaller than those of samples crosslinked with genipin, while EAB values were similar (Figure S2, Supporting Information). In addition, the σ_{TS}^2/E of gelatin crosslinked with TG was approximately two times smaller than gelatin crosslinked with genipin (Figure S3, Supporting Information). Thus, genipin was a more promising gelatin crosslinker than TG, as crosslinking with genipin exhibited higher σ_{TS}^2/E , which was equal to or higher than that of nylon springs, but smaller than that of steel springs (Figure 2e). The mixture with Gel:PVA = 1:0.05 mass ratio exhibited the largest σ_{TS}^2/E (2.8 MJ m^{-3}) and was used for viscoelasticity characterization and jumping experiments (i.e., Gel:Gly:Wat:PVA:Gen = 1:2.5:2.5:0.05:0.01).

Many food materials are viscoelastic and display stress relaxation under strain ϵ .^[47,49] In the case of a gelatin hydrogel, varying the water and glycerol ratio can significantly change its viscoelasticity. Increasing the water content allows for more water molecules to interact with the gelatin chains through hydrogen bonding and hence forms more triple helix chains, improving the gelatin hydrogel’s mechanical strength.^[50] However, without water acting as a lubricant between polymeric chains, gelatin exhibits more viscoelasticity, as more energy is dissipated to cope with friction between gelatin chains generated by deformation.^[51] Meanwhile, adding glycerol can improve the elasticity of gelatin hydrogel for an extended period of time.^[44] Glycerol forms hydrogen bonds with the polar groups of gelatin and reduces the intermolecular interaction between gelatin chains, which reduces the brittleness and increases flexibility by allowing the chains to move freely with less energy dissipation.^[52,53]

The viscoelastic time constants (τ) of four types of mixtures were characterized against tensile strain based on the Maxwell model (Figure 2f; Figure S4, Supporting Information). Note that a material exhibiting large τ displays lower relaxation under strain and better approximates an ideal elastic material. On the

Figure 2. Mechanical properties of our gelatin mixtures measured by tensile test (refer Figure S1, Supporting Information). a) Young's modulus (E) and the square of tensile strength (σ_{TS}^2) of inedible materials used for jumping applications [12,16,20,23,24,27,32–36] and our gelatin mixture (Gel: gelatin, Gly: glycerol, Wat: water, Gen: genipin, PVA: polyvinyl alcohol). The break-off lines correspond to σ_{TS}^2/E , and their magnitudes increase toward the bottom-right corner, implying a greater capability of storing elastic energy. b–d): The material properties of gelatin mixtures (Gel/Gly/Wat/PVA/Gen) during ten days stored at room temperature. The mass ratio of Gel, Gly, Wat, and Gen was fixed as 1:2.5:2.5:0.01, while five different Gel:PVA mass ratios (1:0, 1:0.05, 1:0.10, 1:0.15, and 1:0.20) were tested (b: Young's modulus, c: tensile strength, d: elongation at break). e): σ_{TS}^2/E of our gelatin mixtures crosslinked with genipin and five Gelatin:PVA ratios are compared with σ_{TS}^2/E of engineering materials obtained from [37]. f): The gelatin specimen for viscoelasticity characterization was modelled as two Maxwell elements (η_1 and E_1) and a parallel spring (E_0) [47] where η_1 , E_1 , and E_0 are parameters that need to be tuned experimentally. Gel, Gly, Wat, PVA, and Gen was set to 1:2.5:2.5:0.05:0.01, as it showed the largest σ_{TS}^2/E . g): Viscoelastic time constant τ of four gelatin mixtures at different mechanical strain ϵ . A material with large τ displays less stress relaxation under strain. In the case of Gel:Gly:Wat = 1:1:3, the sample was ruptured when $\epsilon > 0.5$, and therefore, it was not considered.

other hand, a material exhibiting small τ is relaxed more easily upon strain and quickly loses elastic energy, which is not desirable for use in jumping. To analyze the effect of PVA and genipin in stress relaxation, τ from Gel:Gly:Wat:PVA:Gen = 1:2.5:2.5:0.05:0.01 is compared with Gel:Gly:Wat = 1:2.5:2.5

(no PVA and genipin) upon strain ϵ (Figure 2g). In addition, Gel:Gly:Wat = 1:2:3 and 1:1:3 (no PVA and genipin) were considered to study the effect of glycerol and water ratios compared to Gel:Gly:Wat = 1:2.5:2.5. These two ratios (Gel:Gly:Wat = 1:2:3 and 1:1:3) were selected because they were previously

Figure 3. Model-based design of a gelatin shell to achieve the highest jump. a): geometrical parameters for a flexible beam (yellow beam: the cross section of a spherical shell at rest, blue beam: the cross section of an everted shell) redrawn from^[57] where L , t , w_h , R , α are respectively the lateral size, thickness, width into the page, radius, and angular opening of the shell. Point force F and the shell perimeter L_a are referred in Note S1 (Supporting Information) to solve the FvK model. b): maximum jumping height (h_{\max}) calculated from the model with respect to $50^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 90^\circ$, $3 \text{ mm} \leq t \leq 10 \text{ mm}$, and $20 \text{ mm} \leq L \leq 50 \text{ mm}$. Left panel: L is fixed as 40 mm, because changing L into different values exhibited the same result (Figure S7, Supporting Information). Right panel: α is fixed as 90° , where the markers A–E correspond to shell designs yielding maximum jumping height of 0.36 m.

used for the fabrication of edible pneumatic grippers.^[11,38] For Gel:Gly:Wat = 1:2.5:2.5, τ was larger than for the Gel:Gly:Wat = 1:2:3 and 1:1:3 ratios over the whole range of ε (Figure 2g), indicating the substantial importance of glycerol and water ratios. Moreover, Gel:Gly:Wat:PVA:Gen = 1:2.5:2.5:0.05:0.01 displayed the highest τ values for ε up to 0.6 (Figure 2g). Although Gel:Gly:Wat = 1:2.5:2.5 exhibited slightly higher τ values than that of Gel:Gly:Wat:PVA:Gen = 1:2.5:2.5:0.05:0.01 for $\varepsilon > 0.6$, the difference became less significant for $\varepsilon > 0.8$. This sudden decline of τ (from Gel:Gly:Wat:PVA:Gen = 1:2.5:2.5:0.05:0.01) near $\varepsilon \approx 0.7$ is most likely attributed to energy dissipation at the onset of strain stiffening; the cascade deformation of protein fibers can introduce the plastic deformation of hard regions and dissipate strain energy.^[54,55] The corresponding stress-strain curve from the tensile test starts exhibiting strain stiffening when $\varepsilon \approx 0.73$ (Figure S5, Supporting Information). Adjusting glycerol and water ratios and adding PVA and genipin resulted in a gelatin mixture with higher τ . However, some stress relaxation persisted, indicating that elastic energy storage gradually decreases when the shell remains everted (under strain) for a prolonged time, as we will also show below in Section 2.3.

2.2. Model-Based Design

To identify the shell dimensions that result in the maximum jumping height, we modelled the gelatin shell as an elastic beam in two dimensions (Figure 3a), based on the Föppl-von-Kármán (FvK) equations in the quasi-static domain.^[56] The deflection profile $w(x, \hat{t})$ of the beam in response to a point force F applied at the apex (center of the beam) is described by the first FvK Equation (1), where ρ is the density of the beam, B its bending stiffness, and \hat{t} is time. The second Equation (2) accounts for the coupling with the in-plane (horizontal) deflection u , for a beam with Young's modulus E .

$$\rho w_h t \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \hat{t}^2} + B \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + T \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} = F \delta(x) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 = -\frac{T}{Et w_h} \quad (2)$$

The beam must be compressed horizontally at both extremities to allow bending and form an arc. This compression is represented in (2) by the applied axial load T . Please refer to Note S1 (Supporting Information) for more details of iteratively solving (1-2) and calculating the maximum jumping height (h_{\max}).

Here, three design parameters determine the shell geometry: angular opening (α), shell thickness (t), and lateral size of the shell (L) (Figure 3a). We made two pairwise comparisons: α versus t (Figure 3b, left panel) and L versus t (Figure 3b, right panel). The highest jumping height h_{\max} was achieved when $\alpha = 90^\circ$ (Figure 3b, left panel). Therefore, α was set to 90° for the comparison of L versus t , which yielded a predicted maximum jumping height $h_{\max} = 0.36 \text{ m}$ (Figure 3b, right panel). Five different designs yielding maximum jumping height of 0.36 m (A to E in the right panel of Figure 3b) were then prototyped and tested (see Section 2.3 below) to assess model strength.

2.3. Characterization of Edible Jumpers

Gelatin shells were manufactured by moulding (Figure S8, Supporting Information) and were tested for jumping after one day of drying at room temperature to prevent premature material failure during shell eversion. However, due to the volumetric shrinkage of gelatin over time (Figure S9, Supporting Information), it was challenging to maintain specific L and t . Therefore, we manufactured 36 different types of edible jumpers with L between 20 and 50 mm and t between 3 and 11.5 mm (Table S1, Supporting Information); even though these 36 designs shrink over time, some of them stabilize with dimensions close to the optimal dimensions predicted by the FvK model (A to E in Figure 3b). Each edible jumper was manually everted and released to measure jumping heights h_{\max} over six days (Figure 4a–c). Overall, jumping height decreased every day due to the ageing of gelatin.^[46]

Figure 4. Jumping height measurements of edible jumpers in different sizes and their characterization. a): The maximum jumping height (h_{\max}) for the range of L and t by manually everting and releasing edible jumpers on the next day of manufacturing (Day 2), where $h_{\max} = 361$ mm was the highest jump. Model-predicted results A-E (Figure 3b) are compared only on Day 2 due to the limited scalability of the model on Day 4 and Day 6. b): h_{\max} on Day 4. c): h_{\max} on Day 6. Note that the locations of each box plot (in terms of L and t) were shifted from Day 2 to Day 6 due to the dimensional change caused by volumetric shrinkage (Figure S9, Supporting Information). d): Shell characteristic parameter $\lambda_D = [12(1 - \nu^2)]^{(1/4)} \sqrt{R/ta}$ ^[57] of edible jumpers versus R/t where ν is a Poisson ratio, $R = 0.5L$, and $\alpha = 90^\circ$. Note that $\lambda_D < 5$ ensured monostability of jumpers. The yellow markers stand for edible jumpers ($R/t \approx 4$) that were pseudo-bistable for more than 3 days in a row when $5.4 < \lambda_D < 5.52$. e): Comparison of h_{\max} obtained from FvK-based model, and experiment (data from Day 2). The size of purple circular markers is proportional to L . Curve fittings of experiment data was done in a least-square manner.

The highest jump (361 mm) was achieved one day after manufacturing (Day 2, Figure 4a) by a sample with $L = 38.3$ mm, $t = 8.6$ mm. The jumping height matched the values predicted by the FvK model (Figure 3b) for similarly sized designs (A: $h_{\max} = 355$ mm, $L = 42.1$ mm, $t = 9.2$ mm; B: $h_{\max} = 357$ mm, $L = 37$ mm, $t = 8.5$ mm), but was lower for designs with $L < 35$ mm and $t < 7$ mm (C, D, and E in Figure 4a), implying limited scalability of the FvK model to jumpers of smaller size where higher surface-to-volume ratios (Figure S10, Supporting Information) makes them more sensitive to moisture loss during storage at room temperature,^[50] which is not accounted for by the FvK model. The rate of water loss can be reduced by storing the edible jumper below room temperature. However, it will be accelerated when stored above room temperature, accompanied by increased degradation of gelatin.^[58,59]

When manually everted, a shell is said to be monostable if the everted state instantly snaps back to the initial state after release; it is said to be pseudo-stable if there is a delay before the snap-

back transition from the everted state; and it is said to be bistable if no snap-back transition occurs from the everted state to the initial state and both initial and everted states are stable. Here, the stability properties of edible jumpers are characterized by a parameter λ_D , which was previously used to characterize the stability of soft shells,^[57] and its definition is given in the caption of Figure 4d. By using fixed Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.49$ and $\alpha = 90^\circ$, λ_D is proportional to R/t at the end, where $R = 0.5L$ (Figure 4d). Edible jumpers were bistable when $\lambda_D > 5.85$ and therefore, they were not considered for jumping experiments (Figure 4a–c) because they could not autonomously snap back to their initial shape after release. There is a transient region for $5 < \lambda_D < 5.85$ where bistable, pseudo-bistable, and monostable shells coexist. In this region, edible jumpers exhibited pseudo-bistability on random days after fabrication (typically one day, sometimes two consecutive days) except those with $5.4 < \lambda_D < 5.52$, where $R/t \approx 4$. Only two types of jumpers (design #33 and #36 in Table S1, Supporting Information) are characterized in this tight region, and they

exhibited four and five days of pseudo-bistable jumping. Therefore, keeping R/t close to 4 enabled more predictable pseudo-bistable jumping. Although shell size is the most influential factor in the pseudo-bistability, other external factors, such as loading conditions, can affect shell stability.^[60] Shell eversion, holding, and releasing were manually done prior to measuring jump height (Figure 4). Minor variations in vertical displacement during shell eversion and different stress relaxation levels due to manipulation influenced the pseudo-bistability of shell snapping.^[60] These slight differences in loading conditions could explain the transient region of the pseudo-stability ($5 < \lambda_D < 5.85$). Further lowering λ_D (i.e., lowering R/t) below 5 ensured monostability, which resulted in an instantaneous state reversal and jump.

We then studied the FvK model predictions of jumping height (h_{\max}) for different design dimensions L/t at Day 2 (Figure 4e). Although the experimental results are in accordance with the FvK model predictions that reducing L/t increases h_{\max} , edible jumpers with small L (small circular markers in Figure 4e) deviated from the model prediction, probably due to the rapid evaporation of moisture in smaller-sized jumpers as explained in the previous section.

2.4. Application Scenarios

Here we describe two scenarios where edible jumper could be used as animated food. In these scenarios, we replace the non-edible support pillar used for the previous experiments with an edible pillar embedded within the concave side of the jumper. Although the added payload decreases the jumping height of the animated food, it does not require any additional support structure for eversion of the shell. Furthermore, the composition of the edible pillar can be chosen to meet desired nutritional and taste profiles.

2.5. Animated Pet Food

In the first scenario we consider using the edible jumper as pet food (Figure 5). In this scenario, a pet owner unpacks an edible jumper loaded with a petfood pillar and manually triggers the jump to attract the pet. We fabricated three types of gelatin shells (Figure 5a). Type A is the monostable (M) shell that displayed the largest jumping height with a pet food pillar (pillar mass $m_p = 4$ g, diameter = 18 mm, Figure 4b). Type B and C are pseudo-bistable (P-Bi) shells with pet food pillars of lower mass ($m_p = 1.5$ g for Type B, $m_p = 0.6$ g for Type C; diameter = 6.5 mm for both types). Jumping heights were measured over four days and decreased over time, as expected (Figure 5b). The largest jumping height of the monostable shell A was 27 cm on Day 2 (Figure 5b,c; Video S1, Supporting Information), while the largest jumping heights of the pseudo bi-stable shells B and C were 10.8 cm and 1.3 cm, respectively on Day 3 (Figure 5b). Type B and C were bistable on Day 2 but became pseudo-bistable on Day 3 due to gelatin shrinkage (Figure S9, Supporting Information). Thus, the jump heights of Type B and C were not measured on Day 2. Although the jump heights of Type B and C were much lower than Type A, the short delay between the manual release and the initiation of the jump (Figure 5d,e) could introduce an additional factor of surprise for pets.

2.6. Animated Dessert Plate

In the second scenario we consider an animated dessert plate for humans (Figure 6a). For this scenario, the edible jumper is integrated with an edible crunchy pillar (payload mass $m_p = 1$ g, diameter = 8 mm) consisting of a commercial edible straw made of wheat and sweetener. In this case, to avoid manipulation of the jumper, the shell is maintained in the everted state by a water-soluble latch consisting of an edible paper made of starch (Figure 6b). Here, the jumper was monostable, and its size was: $L = 30$ mm and $t = 5$ mm. Larger and thicker edible jumpers were not considered, as the edible latch was too weak to hold their everted state.

When the jumper is placed on a liquid droplet (Figure 6c), the latch gradually dissolves and the shell jumps after a few seconds (see Video S2, Supporting Information). Due to the gradual dissolution of the edible latch, the stored elastic energy is partially released, resulting in a reduced jumping height to 6 cm at best. However, the lower jumping height (compared to the version without the latch) retains fast motion and ensures that the jumper does not fall out of the plate. This can also lower any potential risk to children, whilst minimizing splashing. The variability of jumping time and height due to inhomogeneity of the edible latch and amount of contact liquid represents another surprise element when multiple latched jumpers are placed on a plate along with other sweets and drops of diluted syrup (Figure 6d), resulting in a sequence of jumping events (Video S3, Supporting Information).

3. Discussion and Conclusion

Gelatin is widely used in the food industry (e.g., jelly, marshmallow) as a biologically originated protein and is a popular food ingredient.^[61] Here we described, modelled, and characterized a novel gelatin-based jumper that displays faster actuation and larger range of motion than previously described edible actuators. Furthermore, the jumping performance is comparable or better than previously developed inedible jumpers (Figure 1). The propulsion velocity of the edible jumper that exhibited the highest jump ($h_{\max} = 361$ mm, mass: 26.22 g) is inferred as 2.66 m s^{-1} using the ballistics equation without air resistance (Equation S10, Supporting Information). The kinetic energy output at jumping is: $0.5 \times 26.22 \text{ g} \times (2.66 \text{ m s}^{-1})^2 = 92.9 \text{ mJ}$. This is higher than that of micro jumping gel (25.5 nJ ^[13]), micro elastomer jumper ($100 \text{ }\mu\text{J}$ ^[18]), and thermo-responsive jumping gel (13.25 mJ ^[12]). It is lower than that of an isochoric silicone jumper (324 mJ ^[27]), which was however tethered to an external power source.

The amount of water, glycerol, and other additives should be tuned depending on the gelatin type (e.g., source, bloom strength) and intended application. Lower water content in a gelatin hydrogel makes it more viscoelastic.^[54] Increasing the water content can improve the elasticity of gelatin while decreasing its elasticity modulus (i.e., Young's modulus).^[62] On the other hand, adding too much water weakens the mechanical strength.^[50] However, the latter can be overcome by adding PVA to improve the mechanical stability.^[54] Furthermore, a hydrogel containing only gelatin and water is initially too soft to store elastic energy for jumping application, whilst becoming too brittle to

Figure 5. The application of edible jumpers to off-the-shelf pet food. a): Commercially available pet foods are assembled with three selected edible jumpers (Type A: $L = 38.3$ mm, $t = 8.6$ mm, Type B: $L = 37.3$ mm, $t = 4.8$ mm, Type C: $L = 19.2$ mm, $t = 4.4$ mm). b): The change of jump heights over four days by considering the pet food as a payload with a mass of m_p , where Mo and P-Bi mean monostable and pseudo-bistable, respectively. c): the jumping of monostable Type A, where t_0 is a reference time. d): The jumping of Type B, which was pseudo-bistable; there was 1 s of time delay between the moment of shell eversion (at $t_0 + 0.72$ s) and the onset of jumping (at $t_0 + 1.7$ s). e): The jumping of Type C (pseudo-bistable), where t_0 corresponds to the moment when hands were out of camera angle after the shell eversion. Captured images showing the manual shell eversion of Type C are not displayed.

be mechanically deformed for storing elastic energy after a few days of storage. Hence, for improved texture stability and storage, glycerol (or other sugar alcohols, such as glucose or sorbitol) can be added.^[59] Glycerol was added to improve the elasticity of gelatin hydrogel in this study,^[44] which is supported by the observation of increased time constant τ with more glycerol content (Figure 2g).

The FvK model predicts accurately jumping height of freshly made jumpers, although it cannot explain the decrease of jumping height over multiple days (Figure 4a–c). Gelatin exhibits complex time-evolving changes in rheological and mechanical properties,^[45] and additional parameters are required to capture time-dependent chemical processes. For example, the ageing of gelatin shortens its flexible non-crystallized regions, which is supported by the decrease of EAB (Figure 2d), while the rigid crys-

talline regions grow.^[46] Since the elastic energy storage comes from the flexible non-crystallized regions, the ageing causes gelatin to behave far from an ideal elastic material. Ageing could be slowed down by using gelatin with low molecular weight or by adding salts (e.g., NaCl).^[46] Alternatively, the jumping ability could be partially recovered by putting an old jumper in a humid chamber with 50% of relative humidity (Figure S11, Supporting Information), although the jumpers should not be over-hydrated because the predominance of the hydrogen bonding between OH-groups of water molecules over NH-groups of gelatin chains could cause tears during shell eversion.^[50] Although extensive experimental studies with animals and humans are required to tailor motion and nutritional properties of edible jumpers to preferences and needs of diverse animal species, human cultures, and age brackets, these results bring a novel, fast, and large

Figure 6. The application of edible jumpers in an animated dessert plate. a): Example of serving edible jumpers on a plate with off-the-shelf sweets. b): The everted shapes could be temporarily latched with a water-dissolvable edible paper. The size of the gelatin shell: $L = 30$ mm and $t = 5$ mm (monostable). c): Placing the latched jumper on the top of a water droplet dissolves the latch and triggers jumping (t_0 : reference time); the maximum jump height was 6 cm. d): As a gastronomic example, diluted corn syrup (red droplets) was dispensed over the plate (scene 1), followed by placing three latched jumpers (scene 2). These three stages of sequential jumping (scene 3 – 5) could create an animated dessert. Scene 6: completion of all the jumping.

locomotion mode to the nascent field of animated food^[9] for pet care, animal farming, and human experimental cuisine.^[2,5]

4. Experimental Section

Gelatin from porcine skin (04055, Sigma–Aldrich), glycerol (99%, abcr), distilled water (provided by the campus), polyvinyl alcohol (86–89% hydrolyzed, abcr), genipin (Chibio), meat glue (RM transglutaminase formula, Moo GlooTM), edible paper (FunCakes), pet food (MAX, ASCO), and edible straw (wisefood) were used as received. Tensile test gelatin specimens were prepared by stepwise material mixture (Figure S1, Supporting Information). The mixture was cast in an acrylic mould and dried at room temperature overnight. The gelatin mixture for a shell structure was prepared in the same way and then poured into a half-spherical mould (Figure S8, Supporting Information). After overnight drying at room temperature, the mould was disassembled to demould the gelatin shell inside. The edible paper was cut into a rectangular strip (width: 7 mm, length: 55 mm) with a scissor before being used as an edible latch. For the jumping pet food, the pet food sticks (MAX, ASCO) were cut and drilled at their center to create a hole. Selected edible jumpers for this application had small extrusions at their apex. Thus, the precut pet food could be easily

assembled with the jumpers without glue. The pet food Max (1.84 MPa of compressive strength; Figure S12, Supporting Information) was assembled with Type A jumper to withstand large compressive strength during the shell eversion. Type B and C were assembled with the pet food ASCO (0.14 MPa of compressive strength; Figure S12, Supporting Information). In the case of the latched jumper, the edible straw was used as a pillar owing to its low density and superior compressive strength (Figure S12, Supporting Information). The edible latch was connected to the jumper through two tiny slits (cut by a knife) without using any glue.

The maximum jumping height of the gelatin shell was theoretically calculated using FvK equations, and more details are described in Notes S1 and S2 (Supporting Information). Experimental jumping height was measured by vertically fixing a 50 cm long ruler to the substrate and video filming the whole jumping experiment at 60 Hz using a smartphone (Samsung Flip 5). An image analysis tool (ImageJ) measured the maximum jumping height from the video footage.

Both the tensile and viscoelasticity tests were performed using an Instron 5965 Universal Testing System with the same gelatin specimen (Figure S1, Supporting Information). Young's modulus (E), tensile strength (σ_{TS}), elongation at break (EAB) were measured by uniaxially stretching the specimen with 30 mm min^{-1} of speed. Time, extension, and tensile load were acquired at a 10 Hz data rate. Tensile stress was

obtained by dividing the tensile load by the cross-sectional area of the specimen, and tensile strain was obtained by dividing the change of extension by the original length of the specimen. Viscoelastic property (i.e., relaxation time in Figure 2g) was characterized by stretching and holding the specimen for 120 s (Figure S4, Supporting Information), and the resultant force was acquired at 10 Hz. The gelatin samples were stored at room temperature for at least two days to prevent premature material breakage. The tensile stress was fitted to the Maxwell model (Figure 2f) in a least-square manner using the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm, which was readily implemented in Matlab.

The compressive force and density of the material candidates for the pillar (Figure S12, Supporting Information) were measured from cylindrical specimens. Note that the geometry of edible straw was a hollow, thin-walled cylinder. The bulk density of these materials was measured by dividing their mass by volume. Compressive strength was obtained by compressing the specimen with the same Instron machine at the speed of 1 mm min⁻¹ until the material was fractured; here, the maximum compressive stress just before the fracture was considered as compressive strength. Three types of commercially available pet foods and edible straw were cut into cylindrical shapes, and the diameter-to-height ratio was ≈1:1.^[63] Pellet-type edible wax (Armonia, carnauba wax) was melted and moulded into a cylinder shape (diameter: 19 mm, height: 19.8 mm). Two types of oleogels were fabricated using the method previously studied;^[11] The oleogel A was made of a 1:3:1 mass ratio of ethylcellulose (Roth), olive oil (Bertolli), and carnauba wax (Armonia), while the same materials were used a 1:2:1 mass ratio to make the oleogel B.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

elastic energy, gelatin hydrogel, jumping, robotic food

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